

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME:** Audace**FIRST NAME:** KUBWIMANA**PROGRAM CODE:** DSDD**COURSE CODE :** ACA-401D**PERIOD NUMBER:** 1**INSTRUCTOR:** Dr. Gulma**Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (EUCLID provides access)

The author used the following software: MSWord for office 365 ProPlus on Windows 10 Pro

List your 7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP):

1. Basics in essay writing (EUCLID 2019, 1-4)
2. Plagiarism: academic offense (EUCLID 2019, 5-13)
3. Writing a paper: some rules of thumb (EUCLID 2019, 14-16)
4. Literature review: important tips (EUCLID 2019, 17-23)
5. Style guide: coherence and consistency matter (EUCLID 2019, 24-26)
6. American Versus British English (EUCLID 2019, 27-35)
7. Chicago manual of style (EUCLID 2019, 44-55)

IMPORANT SKILLS FOR WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

1) INTRODUCTION

Academic essay writing is an important and regular task for every doctoral student. The EUCLID ACA-401D coursepack for the first study period has compiled important tools and tips to equip doctoral students with the skills required to prepare high standard academic essays and papers. From the basic skills like getting ideas organized into a coherent draft essay to more complex hints such as how to follow coherently and consistently a well selected style guide or avoid plagiarism by adequately recognizing someone's else work in your essay, the coursepack truly exposes student to the very demanding tasks ahead. Furthermore, the course goes really further deep into the matter by providing useful skills on English writing aspects that one would have mistakenly considered as of common knowledge. For instance, the proper use of punctuations, capital and lowercased letters, written numbers versus numerals, and so on, could easily appear as simple skills of the day to day life of any literate person. However, the coursepack

information on these otherwise common writing skills, provides further clarity on how to best apply them in an academic essay writing. Moreover, the part of the coursepack on American versus British English is equally important as it offers a lot of clarity on the differences and similarities between the two English variants and helps to avoid the commonly committed mistake interchanging both world English versions in an essay. This paper follows the Euclid University guidelines on how to write a response paper (EUCLID 2020, 2-4) and it intends to discuss some major concepts from the ACA-401D coursepack of the first study period.

2) ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

The ACA-401D coursepack kickstarts with important insights and tips on how to write a good academic essay. I found it very interesting that the coursepack is designed in a way that allows students to interact with the content. It provides key information but also raises more appetite on the subject matter, hence inviting for further readings. To be honest, one of the most important reasons why I decided to go for a Ph.D. program is to learn how and what to write. I have a lot of interest in writing and publishing, but I have always felt that I had no required skills and insights to produce reliable written materials. This course is for me therefore a very good opportunity to equip myself with skills necessary to realize my dream of becoming a renowned and credible writer in the near future.

a) Where does one start from?

To produce a high standards essay, one needs to carefully plan. The central and key step as one starts the essay writing process is to analyze and answer the essay's question or task (EUCLID 2019, 1.) Nevertheless, the writer's response to the essay's question becomes only meaningful and relevant if strongly supported by evidence from thorough research on the subject matter (ibid.) Indeed, I think that researching deeply for convincing and well documented proofs to support the proposed solutions is the core of the writer or researcher's tasks.

b) The form matters.

The content is what sells the essay, but I believe that the form is what makes the content digestible. The ACA-401D recognizes the importance of a proper form and provides insights on how to best organize an academic essay. The typical parts of an academic essay are the introduction, the body and the conclusion (EUCLID 2019, 3.) I found this particular part of the coursepack quite useful as it provides a good number of very helpful tips as to what to focus on in each part of the essay text and how to properly arrange ideas in the body part. This is really extremely useful and it comes timely for me while I currently prepare for the IELTS (International English Language Testing System) exam where one important task is actually to write an essay on a given topic in only 40 minutes. In addition to the three main part of an academic essay, there is of course the

reference part which is equally important to avoid plagiarism, a very bad academic offense. Let's discuss Plagiarism in the next part of this paper.

3) PLAGIARISM: AN ACADEMIC OFFENSE

“Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information” (EUCLID 2019, 5.) From my experience with previous studies, I found this to be one of the most challenging rules to comply with in the writing art. To be honest, I was very challenged but also pleased by how the ACA-401D coursepack is crystal clear on this very important matter. It boldly qualifies plagiarism as “unethical, not fair and an academic offense” (ibid.) The good news is that there is a simple solution to avoid this gross academic offense and that is simply to “properly cite the author or source that has provided the information one is using” (EUCLID 2019, 6.)

Two methods to properly cite others' works are discussed in the coursepack. One consists in the in-text citation while the other is to list the works cited (ibid.) In this particular paper, I am using the in-text citation method to recognize the content from sources other than my own statements. A list of the works cited will follow at the end in the form of bibliography or references. The coursepack provides many important hints on technics to properly cite or list others' works. Citing can be more direct in form of quotations or more indirect in form of paraphrases (EUCLID 2019, 6-10.) Listing the works cited has also got some important guidelines in the coursepack and these vary depending on the nature of the cited source.

4) BACKING UP YOUR THESIS WITH STRONG URGEMENTS FROM LITTERATE REVIEW

The coursepack does not only insist on the need to support the writer's proposed solution with proven evidence, it also provides information and technics useful on how the writer should go about reviewing others works to inform an academic essay. The course focuses more on proper English writing styles and it does tackle many of the mistakes commonly committed in English writing. I found this part particularly interesting as it reveals many of the mistakes, I have personally been unknowingly committing such as the proper use of “that” versus “which” or the use of “I” versus “me.” The proper use of punctuation marks is also widely covered by the coursepack, but I must admit that this is an area where I still struggle to perform well.

5) AMERICAN VERSUS BRITISH ENGLISH

English is the first choice as a foreign language in most of countries of the world. It is estimated that about a third of the world's population, some two billions persons, now use English (Encyclopedia Britannica n.d.) American and British English are the two main variants of the World English (EUCLID 2019, 28.) The coursepack thoroughly discusses

some important differences between the American Standard English and the British Standard English. These differences are believed to be resulting from differing national histories and cultural development and the way in which the two national variants have changed correspondingly (ibid.) The coursepack does not only discuss these differences but it also highlights similarities between these two important variants of the world English.

From what I read in the coursepack, and to be honest, I think that the differences between the American English and the British English are quite extensive and can be hard to navigate. Both variants have many difference in pronunciation, spelling, words' and expressions' meanings, Grammar, Syntax, Punctuation, General Usage, and so on (EUCLID 2019, 27-35.) The course highly recommends to be clear on which English variant one is using in an essay and to keep consistent with the same.

6) CHICAGO MANUAL OF STYLE

This part of the course is particularly interesting to me as it was my first time to read about this very important topic. I think and agree that it is very much useful and important to be clear on which style one is applying when writing an academic essay for purposes of coherence and consistence throughout the document. This course is particularly focusing on the Chicago Manual of Style as it is the Euclid University recommended writing style. While the Chicago style helps generally to format books and research papers, its Turabian's manual specifically applies to term papers, theses, and dissertations (EUCLID 2019, 44.) The coursepack extensively discusses the Chicago style guidelines on the use of abbreviations, capitalization, hyphenation, italics and quotation marks, date formats, page formats, footnote, headings and lists, tables, bibliography, and so on (EUCLID 2019, 44-55.)

After reading this part of the course, I realized that, in my previous studies and dissertations, I have been writing without following any particular style guide as I had never been told about this! By the way, I strongly believe that the need for coherence and consistence in writing is not only relevant in academic writing. In fact, this part of the coursepack reminded me of the biggest challenge I experienced when I joined my current employer organization. The team uses too many abbreviations and acronyms in internal communications, and it takes several months for a new team member to be able to fully understand a simple email! So, I really think that every organization should have some clear writing style guidelines for both internal and external communications.

Moreover, the coursepack revealed quite a number of new insights to me such as the use of compound words. It was for instance my first time to see the word "hyphen". When to spell number or use numerals was also quite revealing as I did not know that there was any particular rule on this. I was particularly interested in the section on footnotes, endnotes and bibliography because these have always been challenging for me. While reading this section, I checked a number of books in my office to understand how these guidelines are applied. It seemed to me that some of the books in my office do not follow the Chicago style but probably other existing writing styles. I would appreciate if my course

tutor could recommend some particular papers and books that apply the Chicago and Turabian style for further practical understanding of this tool.

7) CONCLUSION

The first study period of the ACA-401D is a perfect entry into the ambitious learning journey for a doctoral student. I believe that the content is good enough to provide students with a good picture of what it takes to produce a quality academic paper. The different chapters of the coursepack are compiled from well respected sources and a lot of examples are provided to give students greater clarity on every concept covered. I believe that the insights from this coursepack will always serve as a basis for all future academic works I will endeavor to carry out not only during doctoral studies but also beyond. I particularly commend the fact that the coursepack content is quite interactive. When reading through, you feel that it is talking to your weak areas and uncovering your most regular writing mistakes. This makes it very easy to pick the essential message as most of the content applies practically to the everyday life of most literate persons. I would really recommend everyone to read the coursepack even if not for academic study purposes.

REFERENCES

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